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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF RELATIONSHIP OF OBESITY WITH
HYPERTENSION AMONG LOCAL POPULATION OF
PAKISTAN**¹Dr. Shuja Ikram, ²Dr. Sana Asghar, ²Dr. Hafiza Misbah Razzaq¹Islam Medical College, Sialkot²Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital, Sialkot**Abstract**

Introduction: Overweight is a body mass index between 25.0 to 29.9 kg/m². Obesity is a body mass index of 30 kg/m² or higher. Over weight and obesity are risk factors for hypertension, dyslipidemia, and diabetes mellitus. The Framingham Study demonstrated that obesity was about twice as prevalent in obese men and in obese women as in men and in women with a normal Metropolitan relative weight.

Aims and objectives: The basic aim of the study is to find relationship of obesity with hypertension among local population of Pakistan.

Methodology of the study: This study was conducted at Islam Medical College, Sialkot during 2018. In this study we selected 100 patients who was suffering from obesity and hypertension. For this purpose we select the patients from both genders. We design an analysis survey for the collection of data. Data on demographic, socioeconomic and health-related variables were collected with a questionnaire validated in local languages. Dietary data were collected with a food-frequency questionnaire.

Results: The mean and median ages of the study participants were 35 and 32 years old respectively (Table 01). Regarding the self or family history of any chronic disease; 50 (10.3%), and 16 (3.3%) of the total study participants were known hypertensive, and diabetes mellitus (DM) patients respectively, while 82 (16.8%) and 64 (13.1%) have family history of hypertension and DM respectively.

Conclusion: It is concluded that there is an alarming situation of obesity among local population of Pakistan which leads to many health issues like hypertension and CVD. Immediate efforts are needed at a national level to control this problem in Pakistan and possibly the neighboring developing countries.

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INTRODUCTION:

Overweight is a body mass index between 25.0 to 29.9 kg/m². Obesity is a body mass index of 30 kg/m² or higher. Over weight and obesity are risk factors for hypertension, dyslipidemia, and diabetes mellitus. The Framingham Study demonstrated that obesity was about twice as prevalent in obese men and in obese women as in men and in women with a normal Metropolitan relative weight [1]. The Framingham Study also demonstrated that both men and women had an increase in blood pressure with increased overweight. Persons in the highest body mass index quartile had a 16 mmHg higher systolic blood pressure and a 9 mmHg higher diastolic blood pressure than persons in the lowest body mass index quartile. In this study, the systolic blood pressure increased 4 mmHg for each 4.5 kg of increased weight. Insurance industry data have also shown a positive relationship between overweight or obesity with hypertension [2].

Hypertension is a major public health problem due to its high prevalence all around the globe. Around 7.5 million deaths or 12.8% of the total of all annual deaths worldwide occur due to high blood pressure. It is predicted to be increased to 1.56 billion adults with hypertension in 2025. Raised blood pressure is a major risk factor for chronic heart disease, stroke, and coronary heart disease [3]. Elevated BP is positively correlated to the risk of stroke and coronary heart disease. Other than coronary heart disease and stroke, its complications include heart failure, peripheral vascular disease, renal impairment, retinal hemorrhage, and visual impairment [4].

Developing countries are increasingly vulnerable to the worldwide epidemic of obesity, which affects all segments of the population, including men, women and now children.^{1,2} Compared with populations in industrialized countries, those in the developing world appear to be at greater risk of the diseases associated with overweight, and cardiovascular disease has become the leading cause of disability and death in many developing countries [5]. Estimates of the prevalence of overweight in Indo-Asian countries (India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka) based on these cutoff values have not been reported. Further, it is not known whether the revised definition of overweight would be valid at a population level in terms of being better associated with the consequences of obesity [6].

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to find relationship of obesity with hypertension among local population of Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This study was conducted at Islam Medical College, Sialkot during 2018. In this study we selected 100 patients who was suffering from obesity and hypertension. For this purpose we select the patients from both genders. We design an analysis survey for the collection of data. Data on demographic, socioeconomic and health-related variables were collected with a questionnaire validated in local languages. Dietary data were collected with a food-frequency questionnaire. All women aged 40 years or under were asked whether they were currently pregnant. Physicians at mobile examination centres performed a standardized physical examination that included 2 blood pressure readings obtained at least 20 minutes apart from the right arm by means of a mercury sphygmomanometer with the subject sitting. Trained technicians performed anthropometric examinations. Weight and height were recorded while the subject was in light clothing and without shoes. BMI was calculated as weight (in kilograms) divided by height squared. Blood samples were obtained at least 1 hour after the subject arrived at the examination centre; fasting was not required.

Statistical analysis

The data of respiratory function were compared between the smoker and non-smoker groups using the independent t-test for normally distributed data or the Mann-Whitney U test for other distributions. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

The mean and median ages of the study participants were 35 and 32 years old respectively (Table 01). Regarding the self or family history of any chronic disease; 50 (10.3%), and 16 (3.3%) of the total study participants were known hypertensive, and diabetes mellitus (DM) patients respectively, while 82 (16.8%) and 64 (13.1%) have family history of hypertension and DM respectively. On the other hand, 182 (37.4%) and 131 (26.9%) of the total respondents were Chat chewer and smoker respectively

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of study participants

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	2381	48.9
Female	249	51.1
Age (years) [Mean = 35]		
25–34	285	58.5
35–44	125	25.7
45–54	48	9.9
55–65	29	6.0
Marital status		
Single	176	36.1
Married	254	52.2
Others	57	11.7
Highest level of education		
Illiterate	9	1.8
Literate but no formal education	34	7.0
Primary school (1–8)	104	21.4
Secondary school (9–12)	133	27.3
Certificate or higher	207	42.5
Income (birr)		
Low level	139	33.3
Medium level	157	37.6
High level	121	29.1

Table 02 shows the mean values of systolic and diastolic BP according to age and gender. In men, the highest mean systolic BP and mean diastolic BP were among the eldest age group and preceding eldest age group.

Table 2: Analysis of relationship of obesity and hypertension

Factor	Total no.*	No. (%) overweight or obese*	Unadjusted OR (95% CI)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)†
Age, yr. mean (SD)‡	36.8 (17.3)	39.6 (15.3)	1.08 (1.06-1.10)	1.11 (1.09-1.13)
Ethnicity§				NS
Muhajir	1606	554 (34.5)	1.63 (1.17-1.28)	
Punjabi	3536	859 (24.3)	1.00	
Baluch	282	85 (30.1)	1.05 (0.68-1.64)	
Sindhi	1425	293 (20.6)	0.96 (0.61-1.50)	
Pashtun	1072	292 (27.2)	1.07 (0.69-1.65)	
Other	1051	232 (22.1)	0.90 (0.61-1.34)	
Male	4414	1019 (23.1)	0.73 (0.65-0.81)	0.66 (0.58-0.75)
Female	4558	1296 (28.4)	1.00	1.00
Urban residence	3239	1216 (37.5)	2.36 (1.76-3.16)	2.20 (1.62-2.99)
Rural residence	5733	1099 (19.2)	1.00	1.00
Literate (able to read)	2943	845 (28.7)	1.25 (1.06-1.48)	1.25 (1.09-1.44)
Illiterate (unable to read)	6029	1470 (24.4)	1.00	1.00
Economic status¶				
High	1607	492 (30.6)	1.60 (1.08-2.39)	1.56 (1.06-2.26)
Middle	4396	1206 (27.4)	1.36 (1.06-1.74)	1.14 (0.88-1.46)
Low	2969	617 (20.8)	1.00	1.00
Food intake**				
Meat, high	2719	994 (36.6)	2.13 (1.71-2.65)	1.65 (1.37-1.98)
Meat, low	6253	1321 (21.1)	1.00	1.00
Fruit, high	3224	972 (30.2)	1.34 (1.08-1.65)	NS
Fruit, low	5748	1343 (23.4)	1.00	
Milk, high	4431	1027 (23.2)	0.78 (0.66-0.92)	NS
Milk, low	4541	1288 (28.4)	1.00	
Eggs, high	1434	451 (31.5)	1.44 (1.17-1.77)	NS
Eggs, low	7538	1864 (24.7)	1.00	
Rice, high	2220	620 (27.9)	1.21 (0.95-1.55)	NS
Rice, low	6752	1695 (25.1)	1.00	
Potatoes, high	4672	1252 (26.8)	1.14 (0.90-1.44)	NS
Potatoes, low	4300	1063 (24.7)	1.00	
Use of cigarettes or "beddies"				
Current	1412	328 (23.2)	0.82 (0.69-0.96)	NS
Not current	7560	1987 (26.3)	1.00	
Use of chewable tobacco or snuff				
Current	1003	233 (23.2)	0.83 (0.64-1.07)	NS
Not current	7969	2082 (26.1)	1.00	

DISCUSSION:

Discussions around the global epidemic of obesity have often used the future tense for the developing world. We have shown that current rates of overweight and obesity are already unacceptably high among youths. This is of considerable concern for a number of reasons. Obesity tends to track within individuals and populations: obese children become obese adults. This tendency, combined with the continued trend toward urbanization, will serve to seriously escalate adult levels of obesity: we observed a 2.5 times greater prevalence of obesity among urban residents than among rural residents. In addition, there are indications that obesity in youth coupled with low birth weight is the worst possible combination for adult cardiovascular disease and diabetes, conditions to which Indo-Asian populations

are already particularly susceptible [7].

Clinical diagnosis of hypertension requires persistent elevation of blood pressure on repeated visits. However, the mean of multiple readings on the same day (2 readings in the National Health Survey of Pakistan) is considered acceptable for epidemiologic studies and has been used to diagnose hypertension in other surveys. In the National Health Survey of Pakistan, blood was drawn without a requirement of fasting [8]. Diabetes was defined as a blood glucose concentration of 140 mg/dL (7.8 mmol/L) or greater or a history of diabetes. This definition diverges from the standard criterion of a fasting blood glucose concentration of more than 126 mg/dL (7.0 mmol/L). However, our main findings were

unchanged when we performed a sensitivity analysis using the older blood glucose criterion of 200 mg/dL or greater [9]. Thus, we believe that these findings are robust. We acknowledge that some dimensions of socioeconomic status may not have been adequately captured, the food-frequency questionnaire was not validated, and information on physical activity was not collected. In addition, our associations between obesity and health conditions were cross-sectional. However, there have been few high-quality cohort studies in the developing world that have assessed associations between obesity and incident disease, and we believe that reverse causality is not a major problem for conditions that are largely asymptomatic [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that there is an alarming situation of obesity among local population of Pakistan which leads to many health issues like hypertension and CVD. Immediate efforts are needed at a national level to control this problem in Pakistan and possibly the neighbouring developing countries.

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